

Optimizing Off-Grid Solar Solutions for Tribal Electrification in India: Enhancing Efficiency with Renewable Integration and Advanced Technologies

Priyanka V

Research Scholar Department of Economics, Kannur University,

Jinisha CV

Research Scholar Department of Economics, Kannur University,

Ajesh Kunju

*Student, Mechanical Engineering Technology Design, Centennial College,941
Progress, Toronto, ON M1G3T8, Canada,*

Dr. Shaharban V

Associate Professor, Head of The Department of Economics, Kannur University

Abstract :India, a country with a diverse range of Indigenous populations living in various geographical conditions, faces significant challenges in the efficient and sustainable generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity. As the third largest country in electricity generation and consumption, India contends with numerous issues that impede the attainment of sustainability in the electricity sector, particularly for tribal communities residing in hilly and forested areas. The Indian electricity sector experiences transmission and distribution (T&D) losses exceeding 20%, which is more than twice the global average of 6% to 8%, as reported by the Central Electricity Authority. The economic development of the entire country is heavily reliant on the electrification rate, yet India struggles with supply-demand mismatches, infrastructure constraints, and grid stability. This paper critically analyzes the problems encountered in the generation and distribution of electricity to the tribal population through off-grid solar electricity. It emphasizes the need to enhance the grid compatibility of existing systems with renewable energy integration. By using Fresnel lens to concentrate sunlight from various angles to increase the efficiency of solar panels. And we also suggest the Canadian Hiku7_CS7N-MS Brand model solar panel which has a power capacity of 670W. Furthermore, the study suggests potential solutions for addressing T&D losses and infrastructure constraints, aiming not only at tribal electrification but also at providing an alternative approach to achieving sustainable development goals. The recent government policy indicates that off-grid solar is the optimal solution for electrifying tribal areas, highlighting the necessity of increasing the efficiency of these systems.

Keywords: Renewable energy, Tribal population, off-grid solar, renewable energy integration

Introduction

Electricity access is one of the key determinants of economic development in the contemporary world. The importance of off-grid solar energy is increasing day by day, especially across the global south. It is facilitated mainly by the liberalization of the national energy sectors and it has caused a sudden fall in cost by roughly more than 80% since 2009, another important thing is that much of the development in these areas is because of the foreign direct investment Radley & Lehmann-Grube, (2022). UN attributes to accelerate electrification through the deployment of off-grid and mini-grid solar systems as well as through the expansion of grids. In many villages and rural communities around the globe, electricity access has been non-existent or limited. But in this scenario, off-grid solar will help to boost electrification in these areas and help economic development Laura Rodriguez, (2023). In India, many rural areas still lack proper electrification due to the remote location of those areas and comparatively low population density. The process of electrification from main grids to the rural areas causes major investment and losses, which causes the basis for decentralization of the electricity Narendra Gothwal et al., (2018). There are significant improvements in the village electrification between 2015 and 2018 through the expansion of grid coverage. In the year 2018, India has achieved full coverage of village electrification Akter & Bagchi, (2021). India's increasing demand and inadequate access to grid electricity in rural areas, many scholars suggest that off-grid solar power is the potential alternative solution for India's energy poverty and achieving sustainability goals.

There are various challenges faced in the electrification of tribal areas. The geographical characteristics of these tribal populated areas are the major reason for the backwardness in these areas. Apart from this geographical limitation, there are so many barriers such as distributed solar program incompatibility with tribal facility circumstances, additional required development steps that can impact the economics of tribally sited utility-scale solar projects, and lack of tribal land use planning or land entitlement procedures, etc... Beshilas, (2023). Poor grid quality and reliability are the major challenges faced by consumers in rural areas. Transparency in the functioning of the grid is essential for understanding the gaps and challenges faced in India's electrification efforts Heynen et al., (2019). There are various technological advancements also taking place in the area of solar-based energy systems. However, there are centralized solar systems too. But the problem here is that no one solution is possible to apply in every scenario Parimita Mohanty, (2018). So the problem we try to solve here is the issues faced in tribal electrification in rural areas, especially in tribal areas, and how an off-grid solar installation and using recent technical advancement can solve these issues in tribal electrification. India's tribal regions are mostly off the grid and don't have access to consistent energy. Off-grid solar power is becoming more widely acknowledged as a game-changing method for bringing electricity to India's tribal areas. These areas, frequently found in isolated and difficult terrain, have historically had difficulty getting access to dependable energy. Off-grid solar technology adoption has significant socioeconomic and environmental benefits essential to these communities' growth and well-being. Reliable electricity enables the operation of essential services such as lighting, healthcare facilities, and schools. This access can enhance healthcare and improve school hours, that ultimately improves all of the standard of living in native communities. Opportunities for local business ventures and entrepreneurship are created by electrification. With access to power, small businesses like stores and workshops can flourish resulting in

jobs and more economic activity in the region. With reliable power, communities can adopt modern agricultural techniques and technologies, improving productivity and income. Additionally, local industries can benefit from stable energy sources for production and processing. Off-grid solar solutions represent a pivotal opportunity for electrifying tribal areas in India, with significant socio-economic and environmental benefits. By improving access to reliable energy, these solutions can enhance quality of life, drive economic growth, and create employment opportunities while reducing environmental impact. Embracing and expanding these technologies is essential for fostering sustainable development and equity for tribal communities, ensuring that they benefit from the advancements in renewable energy and environmental stewardship.

The primary objective of this paper is to improve the efficiency of electricity distribution, particularly in remote tribal areas, by integrating available renewable energy sources. This integration is crucial for the overall development of the nation and for achieving the targets set for sustainable development. Over the last several decades, countries around the world have made remarkable progress in electrification rates Aklin et al., (2018), *WEO-2017 Special Report*, (2017) Despite this encouraging news, electricity access often remains unevenly distributed within countries. As a result, many of them are excluded from the benefits Aklin et al., (2021a). STs are important social actors in the state's politics Chandra, (2004.). but they are also known to suffer from high degrees of poverty. Socioeconomic disparities between dominant and marginalized groups have been widely documented in India. Scheduled Tribes are considerably less likely to benefit from any electric connection than the general population. About 18% are unconnected among tribal respondents, against only 9% in the general population. The gap is about 9 percentage points Aklin et al., (2021a).

Objectives and Scope

The major objective of this paper is to suggest an alternative method for Optimizing off-grid solar electrification of tribal areas in India. The paper also suggests advanced technological solutions for enhancing the efficiency of renewable energy sources, especially solar energy in the tribal areas of India. In India, the electrification of rural areas remains a challenging issue for policymakers. The geographical conditions and largest population in rural areas are the major causes for these challenges in electrification. Using an efficient method for solving these electrification issues may help to achieve the target of efficient and sustainable energy for all.

Review of Literature and Theoretical Background

In recent years, the quest to meet rising energy demands sustainably has led researchers to explore the integration of renewable energy sources with combined heat and power (CHP) systems. A comprehensive study by Bagherian & Mehranzamir, (2020) delves into this area, emphasizing how integrating solar, wind and geothermal energy with CHP can maximize the utilization of renewable resources. This integration not only promises to satisfy energy demand but is also considered the best approach to leverage the full potential of renewable energy sources. The study reveals three main areas of focus: the development and application of models in solar-integrated systems, thermo-economic optimization in geothermal-integrated systems, and scheduling to minimize curtailment in wind-integrated systems. By examining these state-of-the-art designs, the study aims to enhance the effectiveness and feasibility of renewable integration in future operations.

However, the path to a fully decarbonized power sector is fraught with challenges. Erdiwansyah et al., (2021) critically review the integration of renewable energy sources with various technologies, identifying both solutions and obstacles. Their findings suggest that developing a comprehensive matrix of renewable technology solutions can help address these challenges, thereby improving the reliability of the power sector. Further exploring the impact of renewable integration, Joseph Oyekale et al., (2020) examine the practical effects on grid systems. Their study highlights the need for multi-sectoral coupling, particularly through the promotion of electric vehicle usage and integration with renewable-based power grids. They also point out the necessity for cheaper energy storage solutions, such as repurposing abandoned electric vehicle batteries and advancing thermal energy storage systems.

In India several areas are still lagging behind in the target of 100% electrification especially in the rural areas. The paper titled “Off-grid Rural Electrification in India Using Renewable Energy Resources and Battery Technologies with a Dynamic Differential Annealed Optimization” is discussing about various solutions for accessing electricity for rural areas in India, specially concentrated on Odisha. The study analyses about the feasibility of locally available renewable energy resources and combined with three different battery technologies such as, Nickel-Iron (Ni-Fe), Lithium-Ion (Li-Ion), and Lead Acid (LA). The paper underlines the effectiveness of the Dynamic Differential Annealed Optimization (DDAO) algorithm in optimizing such off-grid systems, and the paper also found that the Ni-Fe battery configuration as the best choice for rural electrification in the rural areas of Odisha (P. Kumar et al., 2021).

In a comprehensive review about the various prospects for the electrification of rural area using stand-alone and hybrid energy technologies, the paper argues that most of the rural areas in the growing nations are highly depending on off-grid based power generation method for their electrification. The paper is a comprehensive review about the enhanced hybrid electrification in the rural areas by using various renewable energy sources. The paper also underlines about the importance of sustainable and reliable hybrid renewable power generation system of operation. Pandiyan et al., (2022).

In a paper titled optimization of solar and battery-based hybrid renewable energy system augmented with bioenergy and hydro energy-based dispatchable source, the paper argues that the hybrid energy system (HRES) can overcome the mismatch between the supply of variable renewable energies and the demand. In this paper HRES system with various renewable energy sources such as, solar, bio. And hydro sources for the tribal and hilly areas are demonstrated. The paper analysed both grid connected scenario and the standalone scenario are simulated. The optimal LCOE of 0.106–0.053 \$/kWh is achieved in standalone mode for 100%–70% reliability. The grid-connected scenario is simulated with two different rates of payment for the electric energy delivered to the grid and a range of grid purchase prices. The LCOE results to around 0.06 \$/kWh for the prospective grid-connected mode cases. The sensitivity analysis and validation of the work are also performed Memon et al., (2023).

Kumar et al., (2016) investigate power quality issues associated with renewable energy integration into the grid. Their research emphasizes the role of power electronic devices and flexible AC transmission systems in mitigating these issues. They argue that efficient integration of wind and solar energy systems through power electronic interfaces is crucial

for the stable operation of power systems, especially when renewable energy sources constitute a significant portion of the total system capacity. In the context of off-grid communities, Kahwash et al., (2021) study the integration and optimization of high-penetration hybrid renewable energy systems to meet both electrical and thermal demands. By comparing coupled and uncoupled system architectures, they determine that integrated systems, which use excess electricity to fulfill thermal loads, are more cost-effective.

Solar energy optimization is another critical area of research. Al-Shahri et al., (2021) provide a comprehensive review of optimization strategies for solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, focusing on reducing emissions and maximizing reliability. They argue that intelligent optimization methods can enhance system reliability and reduce maintenance costs and emissions. The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in revolutionizing solar energy is explored by Mohammad & Mahjabeen, (2023). Their paper covers AI-driven advancements in material research, predictive models, and control systems. By leveraging big data analytics, AI enhances solar cell performance, energy production, and grid integration, underscoring the potential for ongoing research in AI technologies to accelerate the adoption of renewable energy. Urban integration of solar power is becoming increasingly significant. Emmanuel Augustine Etukudoh et al., (2024) review the state of solar power integration in urban areas, addressing challenges such as limited space, shading, and aesthetic considerations. They highlight how emerging technologies and methodologies, including data analytics and IoT devices, boost the efficiency of urban solar energy systems.

Advancements in solar photovoltaic materials are also pivotal for energy storage applications. Dada & Popoola, (2023) discuss recent developments in materials for solar PV devices, emphasizing their potential to revolutionize renewable energy. These novel materials can enhance existing solar panels' performance and lead to more efficient photovoltaic devices. Finally, Udayakumar et al., (2021) focus on technological advancements in the solar PV value chain. They highlight innovations in PV module manufacturing, materials, and emerging application areas. The paper underscores the importance of cell efficiency in reducing processing costs and examines the lifecycle of PV cells, including recycling and end-of-life considerations.

The paper titled "Revolutionizing Solar Energy with AI-Driven Enhancements in Photovoltaic Technology" covers a wide range of AI-driven breakthroughs in solar energy, including material research and development, predictive models and control systems, manufacturing, and development issues, and the application of big data analytics. The paper also looks into how artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms are used to increase solar efficiency, and for maximizing energy production, and enable intelligent grid integration. The paper demonstrates the importance of AI-driven improvements in solar cell performance and their effects on the integration and sustainability of renewable energy sources. It highlights the necessity of ongoing research and development in the field of AI technologies to fully realize the seemingly limitless potential of AI solar energy and hasten the adoption of renewable energy sources around the world Mohammad & Mahjabeen, (2023).

Nowadays the trend of increasing global emphasis on renewable energy solutions has increased and interest in integrating solar power systems into urban areas. The paper about solar power integration in urban areas concentrated on the current state of solar power

integration in urban areas and focused on design innovations, such as limited space, shading, and aesthetic considerations. The review of these advancements provides a clear insight into maximizing energy capture while seamlessly blending solar technologies into the urban fabric. The paper also analyses emerging technologies and methodologies that boost the efficiency of solar energy systems in urban contexts. The integration of data analytics, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and artificial intelligence has nowadays emerged as a means to enhance the monitoring, control, and maintenance of urban solar infrastructure. Through the examination of design innovations and efficiency enhancements, the paper contributes valuable insights into the evolving landscape of solar power integration in urban areas Emmanuel Augustine Etukudoh et al., (2024)

In another review paper about the Philippines off-grid electrification using renewable energy sources, examines the major challenges and suitable solutions for electrification of Philippines by focusing on the use of hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES). This review paper collected various articles published in the year of 2012-2023. The paper highlighted that there is wide range of research papers are existing in the technical and economic aspects of off-grid solar electrification, but there is still lagging the social and political factors Salac et al., (2024).

In the vast tapestry of India's electrification journey, disparities have woven threads of inequality that affect both dominant and marginalized social groups. The research reveals that these electricity availability and reliability disparities are fundamental contributors to welfare gaps between different social strata, particularly based on caste and religion Sedai et al., (2021) The narrative begins with Kemmler's seminal study in 2007, which first shed light on caste-related discrepancies in electricity access using data from the NSSO. It underscored that Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST) faced significant barriers, experiencing limited access to energy services compared to more privileged groups Kemmler, (2007)

Another study delved into the unequal impact of the Rajiv Gandhi Grameen Vidyutikaran Yojana (RGGVY) across caste lines in impoverished Indian states. Their findings highlighted that villages with higher proportions of advanced caste communities were more likely to receive electrification benefits, perpetuating existing socioeconomic disparities Dugoua et al., (2017). Another paper on electrification rates in Uttar Pradesh, reinforces the trend where areas dominated by higher caste communities had better access to electricity than those predominantly inhabited by SC groups Aklin et al., (2021b) Interestingly, Dugoua et al. (2017) found that an increase in lower caste households within a village positively correlated with improved household electricity reliability, challenging assumptions about caste dynamics in rural electrification Dugoua et al., (2017). Saxena and Bhattacharya (2018) shifted the focus to urban areas, revealing how residential segregation based on caste influences electricity usage patterns. Marginalized households often find themselves in impoverished neighbourhoods or segregated pockets where energy providers might discriminate against them, affecting their access to basic amenities like electricity and LPG Saxena & Bhattacharya, (2018)

The research paper titled "Optimization of off-grid hybrid renewable energy systems for cost-effective and reliable power supply in Giata Selassie, Ethiopia", the paper concentrated on the optimization and designing of hybrid renewable energy systems for providing cost-effective electricity supply to rural areas. The study underlines the importance of tailored

HRES designs for rural areas, where difficulties in achieving reliable and affordable electricity for achieving sustainable development Agajie et al., (2024).

Moving beyond mere access, Sedai et al. (2021) explored the quality of electrification and its impact on gender empowerment. Their research, using sophisticated statistical methods, demonstrated that improved electricity access significantly enhances women's economic autonomy, decision-making abilities, and overall empowerment across different socio-economic strata Sedai et al., (2021). In the realm of sustainable energy solutions, the exploration extends to solar energy. Ali O.M. Maka and Jamal M. Alabid (2022) emphasized solar power as a pivotal renewable energy source that not only mitigates environmental impact but also fosters sustainable development. They underscored its potential to stabilize energy prices, generate employment, and support socio-economic advancement, making it a compelling choice amidst global energy challenges Jamal et al., (2023)

Studies further advocated for solar energy as a sustainable solution amid rising global energy demands. Their research highlighted the scalability and economic benefits of solar power, positioning it as a crucial tool in addressing future energy crises while bolstering economic growth in developing nations (Kannan & Vakeesan, (2016). In another paper it examined the implementation of renewable off-grid technologies, emphasizing their role in providing sustainable electricity solutions where grid extension is impractical. Their study underscored the importance of technical, financial, and social sustainability in ensuring the longevity and impact of off-grid projects in rural communities Lestari et al., (2018).

In conclusion, Mishra, (2013) synthesized these insights into a holistic framework for decentralized off-grid development in India. They stressed the pivotal role of policy support, community participation, and productive linkages in overcoming barriers such as capacity constraints, local conflicts, and elite capture. By integrating these findings, they proposed strategies to enhance the operational feasibility and scalability of off-grid initiatives, thereby addressing socio-economic disparities and advancing inclusive development goals. Khaled Obaideen et al., (2021) rounded out the narrative by highlighting the broader global implications of energy transitions towards solar power. They situated solar energy within the context of achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs), showcasing how innovations like the Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park in the UAE exemplify the transformative potential of renewable energy in reshaping socio-economic landscapes.

Together, these studies paint a comprehensive picture of the current landscape and future potential of renewable energy integration, highlighting the technological advancements, challenges, and innovative solutions that drive the transition towards a more sustainable energy future. This collective narrative paints a vivid picture of India's electrification journey, marked by challenges and opportunities, where technological advancements and policy innovations intersect with socio-cultural dynamics to shape the future of energy access and social equity.

The integration of renewable energy sources with combined heat and power systems is pivotal for meeting future energy demand sustainability. This review shows various advancements and challenges in these areas, encompassing model development, optimization strategies, and socio-economic considerations. There are various socio-economic disparities in energy access particularly in tribal areas in India, which emphasize the need for inclusive policies and sustainability. Furthermore, the global indications of renewable energy

transitions underscore their role in achieving sustainable development goals. Thus extensive review serves as a foundation for future research and policy development in this area. We found that there is still a gap in the research about the inclusion of tribal populations in electricity access and sustainability.

RESEARCH GAP

Reviewing the available literature for this study, we found that there is still a research gap in the area of tribal populations in the context of electricity access and sustainability for the tribal population of

India. And this gap will provide a new area for research in terms of how the renewable energy integration and off-grid solutions can be designed to solve the unique socio-economic and geographical challenges of tribal population.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

OFF-GRID SOLAR SYSTEM

A self-sufficient energy option, an off-grid solar system uses solar cells to produce electricity without connecting to the national utility grid. These systems employ batteries to store excess energy for use during times when there is little to no sunlight, as opposed to depending on grid electricity. Off-grid systems offer a dependable and sustainable energy supply, making them perfect for isolated areas or places where grid access is difficult. They provide advantages like lower costs, less of an impact on the environment, and more energy security and independence.

Independently create, store, and supply solar energy without the need for outside resources known as standalone power systems (SAPS), also referred to as off-grid solar systems. By using photovoltaic cells, which are driven by sunlight and composed of semiconducting materials like silicon, solar panels can collect solar radiation. Afterward, a solar charge controller regulates the direct current (DC) electricity produced by this process. Through the use of a solar converter, DC power is transformed into alternating current (AC) that can be stored in a battery system or used for your home.

Figure 1: off-grid solar system

Source:<https://roofgnome.com/blog/solar/what-is-off-grid-solar-system>

WORKING OF SOLAR PANEL

The solar panel works by photovoltaic effect. A p-n junction, which is created by combining p-type and n-type semiconductors, is what allows solar cells to produce the photovoltaic effect. Photons from the light enter the cell and provide electrons in the semiconducting material energy. This energy causes the electrons to jump to the conduction band and leave behind electron-hole pairs. Electrons are driven toward the n-side and holes are driven toward the p-side by the electric field at the p-n junction. An electric current is produced by the movement of charge carriers. The current is called photocurrent. The current is produced by electrons traveling through the cell: holes go in the opposite direction to complete the electric circuit. The below shows the photovoltaic effect.

Figure 2: working of solar panel

Source: *Ecogreen Electrical*. (August 14, 2015)

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR THE RESEARCH WORK

The area selected for this study north-eastern region of India. Includes Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura, Sikkim. The data for the study is collected from various secondary sources such as the official website of renewable energy and the Ministry of tribal affairs (MOTA), Solar Energy Corporation of India Limited, World Information Service on Energy (WISE), and the data set of off-grid solar energy output calculation.

For increasing the accessibility and efficiency of tribal electrification a model of the Canadian HiKu7 with Fresnel lite to concentrate light nearly to a photovoltaic cell.

The following figures (3+4) shows working of off-grid solar system with Fresnel lens

Figure 3:Arrangement of Fresnel lens on top of solar panels

Figure 4: Basic off- grid system

FRESNEL LENS

Pronounced “fray- NEL,” a Fresnel lens is made of plastic with concentric grooves carved into it in place of a typical lens’s curved surface. Its small and lightweight form enables it to focus light efficiently. Fresnel lenses are great at gathering light and come in a range of sizes. They function similarly to conventional lenses in terms of focusing but have additional benefits in terms of cost, weight, and profile.

Figure 3: working of fresnel lens

Source: profile of a Fresnel lens <https://www.edmundoptics.com/knowledge-center/application-notes/optics/advantages-of-fresnel-lenses/#theory>

A Fresnel lens is frequently used for solar light gathering because it can concentrate light nearly parallel to a photovoltaic cell, which is perfect for boosting light intensity on solar panels.

Figure 4: Light Collimation of a Point Source with a Fresnel Lens

Source: <https://www.edmundoptics.com/knowledge-center/application-notes/optics/advantages-of-fresnel-lenses/#theory>

FEATURES CANADIAN SOLAR HiKu7

1. CAPACITY

A major feature of Canadian solar Hiku7 is that it has a power output capacity of 640w-670w. The power output is nothing but the amount of energy the panel will produce in an hour.

Table 1 : Some brand models and their output power

Brand model	Power (wp)	Watt/kg
LG Electronics LG380Q1C-V5	380	21.7143
Sun Power SPR-A450-COM	450	20.8333
LG Electronics LG370N1C-N5	370	20.5556
AE Solar AE595MD-156	595	20.5172
AE Solar AE550MD-144	550	20.3704
LONGi LR5-72HPH-550M	550	20.2206
Jinergy JNMM144(182)	550	20.0730
Seraphim SRP-540-BMA-HV	540	20.0000
Canadian Solar HiKu5_CS3Y-P	550	19.7842
LG Electronics LG425N2W-L5	425	19.7674
REC Solar REC405AA Pure	405	19.7561
LONGi LR4-72HPH-460M	460	19.7425
Canadian Solar HiKu5_CS3N-MS	610	19.6774
Jinko JKM550M-72HL4-V	550	19.6429
Suntech Ultra_V_Pro_N-type_STP570S_C72_Vmh	570	19.5876

Source: <https://solarpoweredblog.com/solar-panel-weight/>

The above table shows some brand models and their output power. It is clear from the table that we need a lesser number of modules to produce the same system.

2. SOLAR EFFICIENCY

Solar efficiency is the amount of sunlight that is converted to electricity.

3. SHADING TOLERANCE

Dual-cell technology

To improve performance and tolerance to shade, the HiKu7 solar panels make use of half-cut or dual-cell technology. The panels essentially become 120-cell modules instead of the typical 60-cell ones by splitting conventional solar cells in two with a laser. Because more cells receive an equal distribution of current, this design lessens the effect of shade and enhances hotspot performance while lowering the risk of overheating. In addition, the panel's dual-cell design prevents a total loss of power if it is partially shaded, allowing the panel to retain up to 50% of its output. Overall efficiency and shading tolerance improve as a result.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Band Gap Energy

It is the energy required to emit electrons from the valence band to the conduction band.

Band gap for different materials

Material		Band Gap (eV)
Si	Silicon	1.11
Ge	Germanium	0.67
CdTe	Cadmium telluride	1.5
Cu ₂ O	Copper oxide	2.1
Cu ₃ N	Copper nitride	1.75
GaP	Gallium phosphide	2.26
GaAs	Gallium arsenide	1.43
PbS	Lead sulfide	0.37
Si ₃ N ₄	Silicon nitride	5
C	Diamond	5.5
SiO ₂	Silica	9

Source: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Band_gap

ENERGY OF A PHOTON

The energy required to release that electron is given by photons.

The energy of a photons,

$$E = h\nu = h \left(\frac{C}{\lambda} \right)$$

Where,

$h =$ plank constant

c = speed of light

λ = wave length

wavelength for the violet side of the visible spectrum

$\lambda \approx 400\text{nm}$

$$E = 4.136 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV} \cdot \text{s} \cdot (3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} / (700 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m})) = 3.10 \text{ eV}$$

The wavelength for the red circle of the visible spectrum $\lambda = 700\text{nm}$

$$E = 4.136 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV} \cdot \text{s} \cdot (3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} / (400 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m})) = 1.77 \text{ eV}$$

Which shows nearly 1 photon is required to emit 1 electron. So, if we increase the number of photons which increases the number of electrons, thereby increasing the photo current

RELATION BETWEEN LIGHT INTENSITY AND PHOTOCURRENT

The intensity of light is simply power per unit, thus we use the following equation

$$|J_{ph}| = EQE \times \frac{q\lambda}{hc} I_L,$$

J_{ph} - photo current density

EQE - (External Quantum Efficiency)

I_L - (light intensity (w/m²))

h - Planck constant

c - speed of light

q - elementary charge

λ - wavelength of light

The equation shows photo current is directly proportional to the intensity of light

Tilt angle

The solar panel gives a better result when the sunlight incident at a right angle. To attain this solar panels, need to be installed at a certain tilt angle. Two things are considered for this, the best tilt angle for solar panels varies with the season and month of the year.

Month	Optimal Angle
January	55°- 60°
February	50°
March	40°- 45°
April	30°- 35°
May	15°- 20°
June	10°- 15°
July	10°
August	10°- 15°
September	20°- 30°
October	35°- 40°

November	45°- 50°
December	55°- 60°

Source: <https://www.renewablewise.com/how-to-increase-solar-panel-output/>

The optimal orientation of solar panels is contingent upon the time of day, as they are positioned to maximize solar radiation throughout the day.

Time	Optimal Direction
5:00 – 8:00	East
8:00 – 10:00	South-East
10:00 – 14:00	South
14:00 – 16:00	South-West
16:00 – 19:00	West

Source: <https://www.renewablewise.com/how-to-increase-solar-panel-output/>

From the above table, it is clear that the better choice is to direct it to the south.

Conclusion

On the basis of the above calculation, we have some suggestions for increasing the efficiency and accessibility of electrification in India, especially in tribal communities. We find that India can achieve the target of 100% electrification by using the technology of off-grid solar by installing Fresnel lens on solar panels to increase the concentration of sunlight and thereby increase electricity. By installing these highly efficient solar panels (Canadian HiKu7) in tribal areas and increasing electrification at a minimum cost with efficiency.

It's also important to think about the cost of importing the Canadian HiKu7 solar model. The fact that the installation of the HiKu7 solar model with Fresnel lens will surely increase the efficiency and it will cut down the system loss there is a possibility for foreign investments with profit profit-making motive that will help to overcome the challenges faced by the tribal electrification and the overall efficiency.

In the context of sustainability, it is essential to incorporate renewable energy resources for the generation of electricity. So, the study underlines solving energy sustainability and efficiency issues as well as social sustainability i.e. accessibility of electricity to the vulnerable society with modern technologies.

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